

**OUR 6TH NEWSLETTER
IS HERE!**

Dear friends, partners and colleagues,

Another busy year for the e-SAFE project is coming to an end.

In this newsletter you will read about many highlights that happened in the last 6 months. Early October, e-SAFE hosted a public event in Athens, with speakers from leading Greek institutions. This was the opportunity to highlight how crucial it is to combine seismic safety with energy renovations, and to have a fruitful exchange with Greek stakeholders on how they are currently addressing seismic issues, and how e-SAFE could benefit them.

You will also find in this issue some updates on the e-SAFE pilots. In Bucharest, e-SAFE partners will meet with residents in January to discuss together and decide on an energy efficient and seismic proof renovation solution that matches their needs. More on this below.

e-SAFE partners are keeping busy too, spreading the word about the project during various events in Brussels and elsewhere. e-SAFE is an active partner of the Built4People partnership, which brings together the whole value chain to accelerate people-centric innovation for a sustainable built environment. You will find more about what we've been up to below.

Happy reading!

Sunny regards from Catania,

Giuseppe Margani & the e-SAFE team

"Combined seismic and energy renovation of the EU building stock - the experience of e-SAFE project" public event in Athens

On October 5th, the e-SAFE consortium organized in Athens the public event "**Combined seismic and energy renovation of the EU building stock - The experience of e-SAFE project**".

During the meeting, e-SAFE experts exchanged with speakers from leading Greek building institutions, such as the Technical Chamber of Greece and the Union of Civil Engineers of Greece.

Speakers addressed the topic of *seismic protection and energy renovation of buildings in Greece*, and reflected on social aspects related to deep retrofiting.

Finally, the event was a perfect opportunity to present the achievements of the e-SAFE pilots.

**Combined seismic and energy renovation
of the EU building stock**
The experience of e-SAFE project

FIT FOR 55: Council and Parliament reach deal on proposal to revise energy performance of buildings directive

After a two-year negotiation process, on 7 December 2023, the Council and Parliament reached a provisional political agreement on a proposal to revise Europe's cornerstone regulation to decarbonise our buildings and homes: the **energy performance of buildings directive (EPBD)**.

The EPBD now includes, for the first time ever, minimum energy performance standards (MEPS) in residential and non-residential buildings. For **residential buildings**, member states will ensure that the residential building stock will reduce the average energy consumption by 16% in 2030 and a range between 20-22% in 2035. 55% of the energy reduction will have to be achieved through renovation of the worst performing buildings.

What's next?

The text of the directive is likely to take several weeks to refine between institutions before it can be considered final. And after this, the formal adoptions within the Council and the European Parliament will complete the process.

[Read the Commission's press release](#)

[Read the Council's press release](#)

Seismic safety must be combined with energy renovation!

Margaux Barrett & Caroline Milne (BPIE)

e-SAFE partners Margaux Barrett and Caroline Milne (BPIE) published an interesting column on the European Council for an Energy Efficient Economy (ECEEE) website in October 2023:

Nearly 50% of European territory is earthquake-prone, posing serious safety risks to citizens. In the last 50 years, earthquakes in Europe have caused tens of thousands of deaths and around millions becoming homeless.

In Italy alone, around 50% of residential buildings are earthquake-prone, while over 80% of the same stock is highly energy-consuming and carbon dioxide-emitting.

In earthquake-prone areas, energy renovation should thus be combined with seismic retrofitting through integrated solutions. There is simply no sense in retrofitting a building for energy improvements if it is hit by an earthquake the following week. Likewise, for renovating for seismic/structural safety without reducing energy consumption and bills. However, the reality is that decarbonisation and seismic renovation are still largely treated as two separate issues. Maintaining this separation can lead to wasted investments and serious human consequences.

Read the column here!

Updates from the e-SAFE pilots

Stay up-to-date on
the pilots

Catania

After a small delay, e-SAFE activities in this pilot will finally resume early 2024. The local Public Housing Authority (IACP), the UniCT team, and the residents continue to work together to make this happen as soon as possible and thus deliver a new, more beautiful, and more energy-efficient building. The detailed design of the real pilot building should be changed due to budget issues and to the structural configuration needed. Therefore, UNICT is working on a new design-configuration of e-PANEL and e-CLT that is expected to be completed by February 2024. In the meanwhile, UNICT is waiting for the green light from the EC to proceed with the new renovation plan and ask for construction permissions.

Timisoara

After concluding the co-design activities last April, for which the outcomes were presented publicly at POLITEHNICA University of Timisoara, the local engineering team is now applying for national funds in the hope of seeing the project come to life. UNICT structural team is sizing the trusses of e-EXOS and studying the relative substructures. UNIBO architectural team is refining the architectural design, and the Mechanical, Electrical and Plumbing design is now completed. SALFO has completed the Bill of Quantities.

Bucharest

After a meeting with residents last April where the team presented the e-SAFE technology and collected residents' aspirations, the design team has been working on a preliminary deep retrofitting project (includes various e-EXOS solutions) that will be discussed with the residents in a face-to-face meeting in January 2024. The goal of this meeting will be to choose together the best solution that matches their needs. Meanwhile, UNIBO is working on the design of the thermal systems, the detailed drawings of the e-THERM solution and the corresponding technical report. Once the design is completed SALFO will provide the Bill of Quantities.

e-SAFE @ Built4People workshop in Brussels, September 25th

In the framework of the Built4People (B4P) Partnership, CINEA and DG ENER organized a clustering meeting on September 25th in Brussels, which gathered innovative EU-funded projects.

e-SAFE was present, together with **NEBULA, DRIVE 0, RINNO, Surefit, InCUBE, INPERSO, EBENTO, FORTESIE, AEGIR, RE-SKIN, REHOUSE**. Participants came to the stage to present the technologies they are developing within each project, how they are applying them to pilot sites and what impacts they are planning to have in terms of buildings' decarbonization.

e-SAFE @ Built4People workshop in Brussels, September 25th

Participants then broke into 2 groups to brainstorm about 1) *Innovative technological solutions* and 2) *Digital solutions, business models and construction workflows*. This represented a unique opportunity to discuss common challenges between projects, lessons learned but also to draft potential policy recommendations in the fields of financing, regulation, and standardization.

Read about the outcomes

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

FINANCING

- TAKE INTO ACCOUNT **WHOLE LIFE CYCLE** CONSTRUCTION IN INCENTIVES;
- DESIGN BETTER TARGETED **FISCAL INCENTIVES**;
- DEVELOP **GREEN PUBLIC PROCUREMENT**;
- FOSTER **GREEN LOANS** TAILORED TO BUILDING PERFORMANCE.

REGULATION

- ESTABLISH MORE PRECISE SPECIFICATIONS FOR **PLUS ENERGY BUILDINGS AND CARBON NEUTRAL BUILDINGS**;
- MAKE **RENOVATION COMPULSORY** AT KEY STAGES OF BUILDING LIFE WITH CLEAR PRIORITIES;
- ENCOURAGE **MORE HOMOGENEITY** IN EU REGULATION.

STANDARDISATION/ CERTIFICATION

- **FAST TRACK CERTIFICATION** IN PARTICULAR FOR CIRCULAR MATERIALS.
- SUPPORT THE USE OF **OPEN STANDARDS** TO ENABLE INTEROPERABILITY.

UNICT researchers @ SHARPER NIGHT in Catania, September 29th

On September 29, UNICT's e-SAFE researchers participated in the ***Sharper Night***, the ***European Researchers' Night***.

SHARPER stands for *SH*aring *R*esearchers' *P*assion for *E*nhanced *R*oadmaps and it aims to engage all citizens in discovering the profession of researcher and the role researchers play in building the future of society.

e-SAFE researchers, during the event that took place in University Square (one of Catania's main squares), engaged citizens in explaining e-SAFE technology, using maquettes and posters; citizens were also engaged in a crowd-mapping activity to collect data on deep-retrofitting at the local level.

Download the posters here

e-SAFE @ the Covenant of Mayors Investment Forum - Energy Efficiency Finance Market Place in Brussels, October 25th

On October 25th, e-SAFE had the pleasure of attending the **Covenant of Mayors Investment Forum - Energy Efficiency Finance Market Place** (COMIF-EEFMP). Successful projects in sustainable energy and climate adaptation funding were presented, shared by practitioners with their peers in various breakout sessions, with the idea that networking plays a crucial role in deepening participants' learning experiences and setting up actionable follow-ups.

Among the projects presented, some of them were of particular interest because they share the same outputs, target or objectives as e-SAFE, such as:

- The *SHEERenov project* in Sofia, Bulgaria, aims to develop a framework for comprehensive residential renovation services.
- The *FINEERGO-DOM* project focuses on ensuring secure financing channels for extensive renovations in multifamily buildings.
- The *FITHOME project*, operating in the Netherlands, targets energy poverty and encourages broad participation in the energy transition.

Read the full article
here

Webinar: Co-designing seismic and energy renovation plans with students and residents: experience from Catania and Timisoara, November 7th

e-SAFE was honored to be invited at the 6th insightful webinar of the *Zero-Emission Buildings Academy series*! The webinar explored the project's unique approach to seismic and energy renovations in earthquake-prone European regions.

CO-DESIGNING SEISMIC AND ENERGY RENOVATION PLANS WITH STUDENTS AND RESIDENTS: EXPERIENCE FROM CATANIA AND TIMISOARA

WEBINAR #6

November 7, 2023
14:00 - 15:00 CET

Vincenzo Costanzo
PhD, LEED Green Associate

Venera Pavone
Urban Planner at UNICT

Nearly 50% of the European territory is earthquake-prone, posing serious safety risks to the building stock. In seismic countries energy renovation actions should be combined with seismic retrofitting. As part of the e-SAFE project, speakers will share how they are involving end-users in the design and implementation of innovative technical solutions for deep energy and seismic renovation.

Leonardo ENERGY
An initiative by
European Commission
BPIE
ECTP
e-SAFE

ZERO-EMISSION BUILDINGS ACADEMY

WATCH NOW

The webinar, organised by Leonardo Energy, BPIE, ECTP and ECI, delved into e-SAFE's innovative technical solutions, implementation protocols, and financial tools to address the dual challenges of seismic retrofitting and energy renovation in earthquake-prone areas.

With speakers from the University of Catania, Verena Pavone and Vincenzo Costanzo, this webinar shared the benefits of involving end-users, as well as the lessons learned from this co-design approach.

Download the presentations here

e-SAFE @ the CCRI'S inaugural Conference: Building a Sustainable Future through Circular Economy in Brussels, November 8th

The **Circular Cities and Regions Initiative** held its first General Conference on November 8th, 2023, marking a significant milestone in advancing Europe's commitment to a circular economy. The conference showcased the dynamic efforts of cities, regions, and their partners in driving the circular transition and fostering social innovation, offering a wealth of insights for e-SAFE's endeavours in constructing low-emission buildings and sustainable building renovations.

Indeed, the importance of embracing circularity principles in the building sector can't be underestimated. This holds true not only for new constructions but particularly for older structures. Circular approaches should extend beyond the integration of innovative solutions in new buildings to encompass the circular requalification of existing constructions. Recognizing this imperative, e-SAFE seeks to change the way we approach building renovation and retrofitting.

FROM VISION TO REALITY
e-SAFE AT THE CIRCULAR CITIES AND
REGIONS INITIATIVE (CCRI) CONFERENCE
Let's Make the circular transition!
8th November 2023

EXPLORE → SHARE → LEARN

e-SAFE @ the CCRI'S inaugural Conference: Building a Sustainable Future through Circular Economy in Brussels, November 8th

The project's approach is not only rooted in reducing material consumption but also challenges the prevailing trend of demolitions. Following one of the Circular Cities and Region Initiative (CCRI) principle, e-SAFE advocates for circular use and life extension of buildings, embracing a business model that minimize waste, maximizes the longevity of existing structures, and employs technical solutions with a low environmental impact.

The Conference was also an opportunity to delve into the financing opportunities for circular projects within the **European Investment Bank (EIB)**. Indeed, private and public entities can now access diverse forms of support for implementing circular projects, plans, and strategies. This opens up extremely interesting scenarios for e-SAFE future follow-ups and strategic exploitation of results!

More specifically, the EIB offers two types of support: advisory and financial. Within its advisory tasks the EIB helps to mitigate risks and improve the investment readiness of circularity projects, supporting the development of the circular economy project pipeline and reviewing circular projects, identifying gaps/weaknesses and advising on improvements. Moreover, the Bank advise beneficiaries on the most suitable financing options within and outside the EIB Group, while facilitating contacts with interested market stakeholders as well. Such services are provided via InnovFin advisory, the InvestEU Advisory Hub and the Circular City Centre (C3).

Additionally, the EIB provides financial support for projects or investment programmes that align with European related to the circular transition. More specifically, it offers loans at highly concessional rates, which can be granted to both the public and private sectors.

e-SAFE @ the CCRI'S inaugural Conference: Building a Sustainable Future through Circular Economy in Brussels, November 8th

The EIB extends its support through various equity services, involving investment or co-investment mainly in funds focused on infrastructure, the environment, SMEs and medium-sized companies. Finally, the EIB also provides guarantee instruments that cover the risks of a single or several projects.

The CCRI General Conference provided an extremely inspiring opportunity for e-SAFE. Learning about other projects' experiences and about new financing schemes for circularity strengthened our motivation to keep moving in the right direction for a more sustainable future. Nevertheless, we recognize that there is ample room for improving the circularity of our solutions, drawing inspiration from other success stories. We can't wait to delve into the circular economy universe, further driving innovation in the building sector!

Upcoming events!

e-SAFE Accademy 2024: trainings for building professionals!

With the aim of sharing the knowledge and technologies developed within the project, e-SAFE partners will host **face-to-face training events** in different countries in the **second half of 2024**. The first part (half a day) will be dedicated to a general presentation about e-SAFE technologies, scopes, and tools. The second part (one full day) will dive into more technical aspects and will be tailored to the local market and building traditions. This is a **unique opportunity** for you to learn more about seismic-proof renovation and see how you can replicate e-SAFE technologies for your own projects!

If you are not able to attend one of these trainings, e-SAFE is also planning a series of **online webinars and video-tutorials in English**, so you can join and interact wherever you are based.

Stay tuned, more information coming soon!

Upcoming events!

New European Bauhaus Festival, Brussels - 17-21 April 2024

With the working title "**Resources for all**", the Festival brings together innovators, creators, scientists, people, and collectives from all walks of life to debate and shape our future that is sustainable, inclusive and beautiful.

The Festival's programme will span four days across four tracks of activities:

- *Forum* - a platform for engaging discussions and the exchange of ideas surrounding the New European Bauhaus.
- *Fair* - a laboratory and exhibition highlighting projects and prototypes that align with and support the core values of the New European Bauhaus.
- *Fest* - a celebration that unites culture, art, and conviviality, serving as a moment of collective rejoicing, honouring freedom of expression and embracing radical, innovative, and disruptive ideas and visions.
- *Satellite events* - events and initiatives organised independently in Brussels and beyond, with core activities in line with the New European Bauhaus values.

e-SAFE partners will be present at the FAIR, come and meet us there!

More information about the festival: https://new-european-bauhaus.europa.eu/get-involved/festival_en

e-SAFE stakeholder community

If you'd like to stay abreast on all news related to e-SAFE and seismic renovations in general, we invite you to join our *e-SAFE stakeholder community*.

Join the stakeholders community

Thanks for your attention!

Be sure to **follow us** on **Social Media** to keep upon all the latest **e-SAFE news!**

Partners

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degli STUDI
di CATANIA

ALMA MATER STUDIORUM
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Deloitte.

SALFO
ENGINEERING & MANAGEMENT

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